

Self-efficacy and its relationship with sports achievement motivation and level of aspiration in emerging football plyers U-17

(A field study on football players for Ouargla and Touggourt regions)

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Abstract

The Object of the study aims to identify the relationship between self-efficacy, sports achievement motivation, and level of aspiration in emerging football plyers U-17, for this purpose, we used the relational descriptive method. On a sample composed of 500 male football players U-17. Chosen as Intentionally, and for data collection, we used three scales (self-efficacy scale, sports achievement motivation scale, and the level of aspiration scale). After collecting the results and having treated them statistically, we conclude that the level of self-efficacy, the level of sports achievement motivation, and the level of aspiration were high, and that there was a positive correlation between self-efficacy and sports achievement motivation, as well as self-efficacy and level of aspiration, likewise, self-efficacy could be predicted according to sports achievement motivation and level of aspiration. On this basis, the study recommended the development of training programs to enhance the self-efficacy of emerging football players has become more than necessary.

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I. Introduction

The recent years witness the increasing participation of young people in training programs and sports competitions. (Badreddine, 2014; Kenioua& Boumesjed,2017). Because sports programs are important for young people in ending various psychological pressures in light of the technical scientific revolution (Zerouga & Nedjaimi, 2020; Mimouni et al,2020; Sadouki,2020). These programs contribute to achieving performance and future aspirations (Al-Janabi & Sayeh, 2014; Houari, et al.,2019). The young football player works during training and competitions to prove self-efficacy, the latter is an important force that explains the achievement motivation (Kenioua, 2018; Ghaouti & Bloufa,2020). Bandura (1982) emphasized that the individual's beliefs about his self-efficacy arise through cognitive awareness of personal abilities, and multiple experiences, whether direct or indirect. The theory of self-efficacy is based on judgments made by an individual about his ability to perform certain behaviours. Self-efficacy is not just general feelings, but an evaluation by the individual of himself for what he can do (Awatef,1993). Bandura (1997) pointed out the importance of adolescence in developing self-efficacy. Bandura (1977) indicated that self-efficacy is the judgment of the ability to accomplish a specific behavioural model. The concept of self-efficacy is described as an explanation of individual behaviour (Bandura,1982). Sports achievement motivation means a player's desire to accept or abstain from a situation (Abdel Halim, 2009). Atkinson (1964) defined achievement motivation as the individual's willingness to achieve success. The definition of Johnson & McClelland (1984) coincided with the definition of Atkinson, where they defined achievement motivation as the tendency to success and the individual's desire to be performing at the level of excellence or is the strong desire to complete goals better. The level of aspiration is one of the most important features, as it is the motivation that collects forces and arranges ideas to raise the level of life from one stage to another advanced stage (Hussein Bakr, 2018). It must be distinguished between aspiration and the level of aspiration; aspiration is a pre-perception, but the level of aspiration is the result of quantitative measurement (Hassan, 2005).

The self-efficacy and sports achievement motivation are essential for players as they face changing situations such as competitor, arbitration, fans, and climatic conditions, which requires their own self-efficacy to help them develop their motivation towards sports achievement (Tod, 2014). Self-

efficacy is also linked to the level of aspiration, As the latter is the motive that leads the individual to the best (Al-Mashikhi, 2009). As long as aspiration exists with the player, He seeks to develop his skills and capabilities and achieve the desired goals (Kenioua,2018; Labane et al.,2017).

It was noted that the conditions of playing football in the emerging categories in the southern desert areas suffer from a lack of facilities necessary for training and playing the game in appropriate conditions, and neglecting these categories compared to the senior category. In addition to the difficult geographical and environmental conditions, and the absence of proper planning and preparation, which led to the birth of unprepared players, physically, skilfully, behaviourally and psychologically. Accordingly, the southern players have not appeared in the professional clubs of the highest level, perhaps the reason behind the lack of appearance is the psychological factor, which requires self-evaluation and organization of their thoughts, actions and emotions. with the absence of such studies in the local environment and at the target age group, the need for such studies has been compelled. And identifying the level of self-efficacy, sports achievement motivation, and the level of aspiration and the relationship between them, enables building a constructive strategy for emerging players in the southern desert areas. The current study aimed to reveal the level of self-efficacy, the level of sports achievement motivation, and the level of aspiration of emerging football players. And the Knowing of the relationship between the self-efficacy, sports achievement motivation and the level of aspiration. And verify the extent of the predictability of self-efficacy in the light of both the sports achievement motivation and the level of aspiration.

Therefore, the following questions can be asked:

- 1- What is the level of self-efficacy, sports achievement motivation, and the level of aspiration of football players?
- 2- Is there a statistically significant correlation between self-efficacy and the sports achievement motivation, as well as self-efficacy and the level of aspiration?
- 3- Can self-efficacy be predicted according to sports achievement motivation and level of aspiration?

II. 2.Method and Materials

2.1. Participants

The study sample consisted of 644 emerging football players U-17, which represented all members of the study population through a complete census of the four groups (D.E.F.G); 28 teams from the regions of Touggourt and Ouargla (Regional Association Ouargla -Algeria, 2018/2019 <https://www.lrfouargla.com/>). After distribution and receipt, the number of forms reached 530, and after review, 30 forms were rejected, and 500 forms were accepted.

2.2. Materials

Three scales were applied to collect data, the first scale was self-efficacy scale that was developed by Al-Adel (2001) based on scales were used in many cultures, such as Wheeler & Ladd (1982) and Schwarzer et al. (1997). The second scale was sports achievement motivation scale that was developed by Willis (1982), the Arabic version was developed by Allawi (1998). The scale consists of two dimensions; dimension of desire to succeed (motive to achieve success) and fear of failure dimension (motive to avoid failure. The third scale was the level of aspiration scale that was developed by Moawad & Abdel-Azim (2005). The scale consists of 36 items and four dimensions (Optimism, Ability, Accept the new, Endure the frustration). The validity (Discriminant validity Table1) and reliability (Table2) of the scales were confirmed; where the coefficients of the Alpha Cronbach were between 0.80 and 0.91.

Table.1 Discriminant validity of scales

Scales/dimensions	Degrees of the upper third			Degrees of the lower third			T-test	DF	Sig.	
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD				
Self-efficacy	06	121	5.60	06	154	9.02	11.95	10	0.05	
Sport achievement motivation	Desire to succeed	06	31.15	3.06	06	43.85	1.94	08.56	10	0.05
	Fear of failure	06	24.50	3.93	06	35.66	1.50	06.48	10	0.05
	Total	06	55.65	4.32	06	79.50	1.87	7.27	10	0.05
Level of aspiration	Optimism	06	20.33	02.65	06	29.66	03.14	05.55	10	0.05
	Ability	06	15.00	01.26	06	26.66	02.50	10.18	10	0.05
	Accept the new	06	13.33	02.25	06	20.50	02.50	05.20	10	0.05
	Endure the frustration	06	10.33	01.21	06	15.50	01.21	06.89	10	0.05
	Total	06	59	03.30	06	92.30	04.20	07	10	0.05

Table .2 reliability of scales

Scales/dimensions		Cronbach alpha coefficient
Self-efficacy		.811
Sport achievement motivation	Desire to succeed	.881
	Fear of failure	.805
	Total	.903
Level of aspiration	Optimism	.911
	Ability	.814
	Accept the new	.801
	Endure the frustration	.830
	Total	.888

1. Statistical Analysis

Data analyses were applied by using the statistical packet for social sciences (SPSS) 26.00 software program. The Mean (M), Std. Deviation (SD), Pearson Correlation, and Linear Regression were used in the main study. Additionally, alpha-Cronbach was used in exploration study.

III. Results:

In table 03, the results showed that the level of self-efficacy was high (M=2.80, SD=1.009). The level of sports achievement motivation was high (M=3.46, SD=1.164). The level of aspiration was also high (M=2.99, SD=0.862),

Table. 3 The means and standard deviations

Scale	Dimensions	N	M	S D
Self-efficacy		500	2.80	1.009
Sport achievement motivation	Desire to succeed	500	3.92	1.165
	Fear of failure	500	3.00	1.166
	Total	500	3.46	1.164
Level of aspiration	Optimism	500	3.50	0.882
	Ability	500	2.98	0.814
	Accept the new	500	2.93	0.858
	Endure the frustration	500	3.01	0.891
	Total	500	2.99	0.819

Table. 4 Pearson correlation coefficients

Scale	SE	DS	FF	SMA	Op	Ab	AN	EF	LA
SE	1								
DS	.482**	1							
FF	-.226**	-.203**	1						
SMA	.240**	.695**	.563**	1					
Op	.522**	.534**	-.283**	.243**	1				
Ab	.494**	.494**	-.243**	.123**	.596**	1			
AN	.271**	.345**	-.133**	.194**	.277**	.158**	1		
EF	.304**	.424**	-.186**	.221**	.541**	.403**	.172**	1	
LA	.568**	.574**	-.298**	.266**	.862**	.775**	.555**	.676**	1

1. SE; Self-efficacy, DS; Desire to succeed, FF; Fear of failure, SMA; Sport achievement motivation, Op; Optimism, Ab; Ability, AN; accept the new, Ef; Endure the frustration, LA; Level of aspiration, 2. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It was clear from Table (04) that there was a positive correlation between the degrees of self-efficacy and the total degree of sports achievement motivation, as well as the dimension of desire to succeed. But there was a negative correlation between the degrees of self-efficacy and fear of failure dimension. And There was a positive correlation between the degrees of self-efficacy and the level of aspiration in the total degree and all dimensions (optimism, ability, accept new, and endure frustration. There was also a positive correlation between the total degree of sports achievement motivation and the degrees of aspiration level in all its dimensions, as well as the dimension of desire to succeed. But There was a negative correlation in the fear of failure dimension and the aspiration level in all its dimensions, all values were statistically significant at the level of significance (0.01).

The results in Table (05) showed that (33%) of the variation in the sports achievement motivation and the level aspiration could be predicted by using the Prediction Model, Therefore, the following predictive process could be extracted: self-efficacy = 60.20 + 0.62 x level of aspiration + 0.18 x sports achievement motivation. The prediction equation is statistically significant, and the values of regression coefficients indicated that the relationship between self-efficacy and predictive independent variables was positive; whenever the level of aspiration changes to a degree, the self-efficacy accompanies it with (62%), and whenever the sports achievement motivation changes to a degree, the self-efficacy accompanies it with (18%),

from the above, it was found that there was a strong direct relationship between self-efficacy and predictive independent variables.

Table .5 Regression analysis for the dependent variable self-efficacy and independent variables

Independent variables	Regression coefficient	Standard error	Beta	F	Sig	R Square
Constant	60.20	5.89	/	122.98	0.00	0.33
Sport achievement motivation	0.18	0.07	0.09			
Level of aspiration	0.62	0.04	0.54			

It was clear from Figure (01) that the histogram follows a natural distribution, and Figure (02) representing the Pp-plot graph showed that the data collects around the straight line, so the residuals are distributed according to the normal distribution, which is a condition of the regression test.

Figure (01) the frequency hierarchy of data distribution in regression analysis

Figure (02) graph of residual distribution in regression analysis

IV. Discussion:

The level of self-efficacy is high for football players; as the emerging player seeks to raise the challenge and train to develop the level of performance and keep pace with the requirements of the competition, “the athletes that have a high level of self-efficacy train continuously for long periods and make great efforts during exercises and competitions, and are characterized by positive thoughts and emotions” (Tod, 2014). The results of the current study were consistent with the results of studies (Shelangoski &

Weber,2014; Cetinkalp & Turksoy,2011; Villani et al.,2015); where the results confirmed that the levels of high self-efficacy give a high level of performance. The capability to perform well under different circumstances, self-confidence and perseverance to reach the goal, are the characteristics of an individual who has a high self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997). The level of sports achievement motivation is high for football players, and the mean value of the dimension of desire to succeed is greater than the fear of failure dimension; it can be said that the link between the drive for athletic achievement and success is clear, the strong desire to succeed is matched by great work and effort in the assigned task. The achievement motivation is a personal trait (McClelland, 1961; Atkinson,1974); when the desire to succeed is greater than the fear of failure in this case, it can be said that there is a high achievement motivation, but when the fear of failure is a very important factor, in this case the motivation achievement motivation is low (Jarvis,2006; Khouilidi et al.,2019). Weinberg & Gould (2015) noted that a high sports achievement motivation means a high and strong motive to achieve success. The motive to achieve success can explain the player's performance. On the other hand, the motive to avoid failure does not explain the player's performance at all, and the motive to achieve success is a true indicator of predicting the player's performance (Zuber & Conzelmann,2014). The level of aspiration is also high for football players, due to the capability of the emerging individual to set the goals, plan for the future, that was consistent with the definition of the level of aspiration "It is the level of progress and success that an individual wants to reach, through his capabilities and making use of his previous experiences" (Al-Mashikhi, 2009). The level of aspiration is positively correlated with the fundamentals of success such as creativity, challenge, future goal setting and sports practice (Peter et al., 2011; Montgomery, 2010).

The positive correlations between self-efficacy and sports motivation are attributed to the fact that emerging players are constantly training and working hard, and do not care about failure, Bandura (1977) emphasized that "self-efficacy increases the value of success and reduces the value of failure", Players with high self-efficacy believe that they are able to face various difficulties, and their motivation for achievement is stronger(Gao, Lochbaum & Podlog,2011). Schunk (1995) also noted that there is a correlation between self-efficacy and achievement motivation in sports performance and self-efficacy helps to predict motivation. The positive

correlation between self-efficacy and level of aspiration means that the higher the self-efficacy, the higher the level of aspiration of the players, Bandura (1997) referred that the individuals with high self-efficacy set difficult goals and are committed to reaching them; meaning that they have high aspirations. The results of the current study were consistent with the results of the studies (Chen, 2014; Boussder, 2013; Al-Mishakhi, 2009). Researchers agree that the emerging player seeks challenge and continuity in training, and works to set goals for his sporting life and planning for the future, and a strong desire to succeed despite difficulties (especially in the desert environment, the distance of the houses from each other, the distance from the home from the stadium, and the transportation for the competition), all this explains that the level of self-efficacy, sports achievement motivation, and the level of ambition is high. The emerging player also performs distinctive behaviours by imitating adults and famous players, seeking to reach an advanced level as quickly as possible, to prove his presence in front of others, and to search for a better position among adults or in high-level teams, and why not reach the national teams.

There is a positive correlation between the sports achievement motivation and the level of aspiration, as well as the case for the dimension of desire to succeed, and vice versa for fear of failure dimension, the higher it was, the lower the level of aspiration. Individuals with higher achievement motivation are more interested in future goals than others, as they have a greater future perspective, which explains their high level of aspiration. Raghad (2015) indicated that individuals who achieve high levels of success have a high level of aspiration and vice versa. The higher the level of ambition of the athlete, the more able to achieve, achieving goals depends on the player's motivation, willingness to achieve, and good use of his own capabilities (Al-Karawi & Abd Muhammad, 2014). It is noticeable that the higher the player's beliefs and personal convictions of the ability to perform the tasks, the greater their success rate, and they do not care about the causes of failure, and the higher their ambitions to achieve the desired goal.

The prediction equation confirms that the relationship between self-efficacy and predictive independent variables is positive; The higher the sports achievement motivation and the level of aspiration, the higher the self-efficacy. Bandura (1977) pointed out that the capability to accomplish is formed through external and internal forces, once the cycle of action is chosen, our behaviour is affected by it, and thus we develop a perception of self-efficacy that affects our future decisions. Underlining future goals and

seeking to achieve them enhances the self-efficacy (Pajares, 1996). Self-efficacy can be predicted according to the level of aspiration (Bindu & Padmanabham,2016; Scott,2010). It can be said that the extent to which the sports achievement motivation contributes to the prediction of self-efficacy is through the desire for success, orientation to the future, perseverance and the achievement of specific goals. As for the level of aspiration, it contributes to predicting self-efficacy through a sense of the value of work and life, and it is a greater cause for happiness and satisfaction, and increases self-confidence, acceptance of self and others, and an optimistic outlook for the future.

V. Conclusion:

By presenting and discussing the results, it became clear that the level of self-efficacy, the level of sports achievement motivation, and the level of aspiration were high for football players. There was a positive correlation for football players, between self-efficacy and sports achievement motivation, self-efficacy and level of aspiration, and between sports achievement motivation and level of aspiration. And self-efficacy could be predicted according to sports achievement motivation and level of aspiration. During training and sports competition situations, it became necessary to know and study the positive psychological elements of the emerging players, that helps them achieve their goals, Coaches should also pay attention to the effort made by the emerging player, not the result.

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